

ATTRACTING FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENTS**Shermuhammedov Bekhzodjon Usmonovich**

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Abstract: In this article, foreign investments, the content of direct investments, ways of attracting them, the role of investments in the development of Uzbekistan, as well as increasing the attractiveness of the investment environment and the right proposals and recommendations aimed at attracting foreign direct investments are highlighted.

Key words: investment, investment climate, investment attractiveness, foreign direct investment, economic growth.

Introduction: In the conditions of globalization, the role of investment cooperation between countries in international economic relations is increasing. In order to ensure stable economic growth in the countries of the world, wide use of foreign investments and expansion of their size is becoming one of the main issues. Tasks to be performed in this area in the next five years were defined in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" No. PF-60. According to this regulatory document, during these years, the government of Uzbekistan declared the attraction of foreign direct investments as one of its main policies and priorities, and by increasing the dynamics of high economic growth and attracting investments into the economy, it solved existing social problems, in particular, the level of unemployment and poverty. It was determined that it is possible to

achieve. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities", which came into force on January 27, 2020, guaranteed protection against the unlimited withdrawal of funds from our country and the nationalization of investments [2]. It is also important to emphasize that the Council of Foreign Investors under the President, established in November 2019, has become a new expanded platform for communication with foreign investors, experts and business circles.

Main part: Several economists have mentioned that the importance of investment occupies the highest place in the economy. As an example, we can show the thoughts of John Keynes, one of our scientists who made the greatest contribution to the economy. His investment book, *Retrospective: Investment innovator*, is a valuable resource for today's economy. In this book, Keynes gives several theoretical and practical recommendations on investment. One of his most famous pieces of advice was, "Be greedy when others are fearful." In other words, it is not always beneficial to agree with others on investment.

B.A. Vakhobov states that foreign direct investments are long-term investments that allow the investor to have effective control over economic activity, at least 10% of the company's share or shareholders' capital. .

A.S. Azizov emphasizes that the term foreign direct investment should be understood as an investment in a foreign enterprise by providing partial or complete control over economic activity.

Results and discussion: The main step in the field of improving the investment climate is the formation of a complete and effective institutional framework through efforts aimed at creating conditions for attracting private and foreign direct investment.

World experience shows that any country that has pursued an active investment policy has achieved stable growth of its economy. Therefore, it is no exaggeration to say that investment is the "driver of the economy". With the investment, new technologies, advanced experiences, and highly qualified

specialists will enter various industries and sectors, regions, and entrepreneurship will develop rapidly.

The volume of foreign direct investments attracted to the economy of Uzbekistan (2012-2021)

Direct foreign investments in Uzbekistan	
year	Cash flow (USD)
2021	3,4 \$ billion
2020	3,5 \$ billion
2019	2.32 \$ billion
2018	1.4 \$ billion
2017	1.80 \$ billion
2016	1.66 \$ billion
2015	1.04 \$ billion
2014	0.81 \$ billion
2013	0.69 \$ billion
2012	0.74 \$ billion

In Table 1 above, the total amount of investment projects entered into the country is given in comparison with the years. We can see that the volume of investments in the Republic of Uzbekistan is increasing. However, due to the pandemic that occurred in 2020, the volume of investment slowed down again.)

Summary: Ensuring rapid modernization and technical re-equipment of enterprises operating in our country today, new high-tech automotive and gas-chemical, electrical engineering and textiles, food and pharmaceuticals, information and telecommunications networks and other areas. and conducting an active investment policy aimed at the organization of modern production facilities is given priority attention.

The purpose of granting these privileges is to increase the potential of the real sector of our economy by attracting more foreign investments, to establish new production enterprises based on modern technologies in the regions of our country, to increase new jobs, and ultimately to develop our country in a stable and balanced economic and social manner.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. James E. Anderson, Mario Larch, Yoto V. Yotov. Trade and Investment in the Global Economy. Journal of NBER Working Paper No. 23757 (2017) 1879-1913. <https://www.nber.org/papers/w23757>.
2. The State Program of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the implementation of the strategy of actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of supporting active entrepreneurship, innovative ideas and technologies" on" Decree. No. PF-5308 of January 22, 2018
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 25, 2019 "On Investment and Investment Activities" ORQ-598, Article 3.
4. A.Sh. Bekmurodov. Foreign investments. - Tashkent: Economy. - T. - Study guide.
5. A.B. Vakhobov. Foreign investments. - Tashkent: Finance, 2010. - T. - Study guide.
6. A.S. Azizov. (2021) Reducing financial, economic and country risks in attracting foreign direct investment. Iqt. science. tall fake dr. (PhD) diss. Autoref. - Tashkent: 2021. - 11 p.
7. G.M. Galeeva and E.N. Kadeeva. Problems of attracting foreign direct investment into the regional economy. Journal of Physics: Conference Series, 1730(2021) 012118, 2020. – P. 8.
8. From the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev to the Parliament on December 28, 2018 "On the most important priority tasks for the development of our country in 2019".